

**NONDEFECTIVE INTEGERS WITH RESPECT TO CERTAIN
LUCAS SEQUENCES OF THE SECOND KIND**

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Abstract

Let $v(a, b)$ denote the Lucas sequence of the second kind defined by the second-order recursion relation $v_{n+2} = av_{n+1} + bv_n$ with initial terms $v_0 = 2$ and $v_1 = a$, where a and b are integers. The positive integer m is said to be nondefective if $v(a, b)$ contains a complete system of residues modulo m . All possibilities for m to be nondefective are found when $b = \pm 1$. This paper generalizes results of Avila and Chen for the Lucas sequence $\{L_n\} = v(1, 1)$.

1. Introduction

Consider the sequence $w = w(a, b)$ satisfying the second-order linear recursion relation

$$w_{n+2} = aw_{n+1} + bw_n \tag{1}$$

with discriminant $D = a^2 + 4b$, where the parameters a and b and the initial terms w_0 and w_1 are all integers and $\gcd(a, b) = 1$. We specify two special recurrences, the Lucas sequence of the first kind (LSFK) $u = u(a, b)$ with initial terms $u_0 = 0$ and $u_1 = 1$, and the Lucas sequence of the second kind (LSSK) $v = v(a, b)$ with initial terms $v_0 = 2$ and $v_1 = a$. Given the recurrence $w(a, b)$ and the positive integer m , we let $z_w(m)$, called the rank of appearance of m in w , or simply the rank of m in w , denote the least positive integer r , if it exists, such that $w_r \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$. Throughout this paper, p will denote a prime and m will denote a positive integer.

The positive integer m is said to be *defective with respect to $w(a, b)$* , or simply *defective* if the recurrence $w(a, b)$ is given, if $w(a, b)$ contains an incomplete system of residues modulo m . Otherwise, m is said to be *nondefective* with respect to $w(a, b)$. Shah [12] proved that the prime p is defective with respect to the Fibonacci

sequence $\{F_n\} = u(1, 1)$ if $p \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{10}$ or $p \equiv 13$ or $17 \pmod{20}$, while 2, 3, 5, and 7 are nondefective with respect to the Fibonacci sequence. Bruckner [2] proved the remaining cases that p is defective with respect to $\{F_n\}$ if $p > 7$ with $p \equiv 3$ or $7 \pmod{20}$. Somer [13] partially generalized the results of Shah and Bruckner by showing that p is defective with respect to $u(a, 1)$ if $p > 7$, $p \nmid D = a^2 + 4$, and $p \not\equiv 1$ or $9 \pmod{20}$. Schinzel [11] completely generalized the results of Shah and Bruckner by proving Theorem 1.1 below.

Theorem 1.1. *Consider the LSFK $u(a, 1)$. Then p is defective if $p > 7$ and $p \nmid D = a^2 + 4$.*

Li [8] also proved Theorem 1.1 by extending the methods of Somer [13].

Somer [13] also obtained similar results to those in Theorem 1.1 by considering the LSFK $u(a, -1)$.

Theorem 1.2. *Consider the LSFK $u(a, -1)$. Then p is defective if $p \geq 5$ and $p \nmid D = a^2 - 4$.*

In [4], Burr found all nondefective integers m with respect to the Fibonacci sequence. This result will be given in Theorem 2.1. In [16], we generalized Burr's result by finding all nondefective integers m with respect to the LSFK $u(a, \pm 1)$. These results are given in Theorems 2.3 and 2.4. In [1], Avila and Chen analogously determined all nondefective integers with respect to the Lucas sequence $\{L_n\} = v(1, 1)$. This result is presented in Theorem 2.2. In this paper, we will extend Avila and Chen's result by finding all nondefective integers m with respect to the LSSK $v(a, \pm 1)$. These results are given in Theorems 2.5 and 2.7.

Associated with the recurrence $w(a, b)$ is the characteristic polynomial

$$f(x) = x^2 - ax - b \tag{2}$$

with characteristic roots α and β and discriminant $D = a^2 + 4b = (\alpha - \beta)^2 \neq 0$. By the Binet formulas, if $D \neq 0$, then

$$u_n = \frac{\alpha^n - \beta^n}{\alpha - \beta}, \quad v_n = \alpha^n + \beta^n, \tag{3}$$

while if $D = 0$, then

$$u_n = n\alpha^{n-1}, \quad v_n = 2\alpha^n. \tag{4}$$

It was shown in [6, pp.344-345] that $w(a, b)$ is purely periodic modulo m if $\gcd(b, m) = 1$. We will usually take b to be equal to ± 1 , so that $w(a, b)$ will then automatically be purely periodic modulo m . Since $u_0 = 0$, we see that $z_u(m)$ exists for all m such that $\gcd(m, b) = 1$. From here on, we assume that $\gcd(p, b) = \gcd(m, b) = 1$. The *period* of $w(a, b)$ modulo m , denoted by $\lambda_w(m)$, where $\gcd(m, b) = 1$, is the least positive integer c such that $u_{n+c} \equiv u_n \pmod{m}$ for all $n \geq 0$.

Given the recurrence w , we let $A_w(d, m)$ denote the number of times that the residue d appears in a full period of w modulo m . Clearly, m is nondefective with respect to w if $A_w(d, m) \geq 1$ for all residues d modulo m . We define $S_w(m)$ to be the set of all residues $i \in \{0, 1, \dots, m - 1\}$ such that $A_w(i, m) \geq 1$.

The following results will be useful for our future work.

Theorem 1.3. *Consider the recurrence $w(a, b)$. Suppose that m is defective. Then every positive multiple of m is also defective.*

This is proved in Theorem 2 of [12] for the Fibonacci sequence. The proof is completely similar for the recurrence $w(a, b)$.

Theorem 1.4. *Consider the recurrence $w(a, b)$. If m is nondefective with respect to $w(a, b)$, then m is nondefective with respect to $u(a, b)$.*

Proof. Suppose that m is nondefective with respect to $w(a, b)$. Since $w(a, b)$ is purely periodic modulo m and $A_w(0, m) \geq 1$, we can assume without loss of generality that $w_0 \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$. If $d = \gcd(w_1, m) > 1$, then by the recursion relation (1) defining $w(a, b)$, $d \mid w_n$ for all $n \geq 0$ and $A_w(1, m) = 0$, contrary to assumption. Thus, $w_1 \equiv c \pmod{m}$, where c is invertible modulo m . Then by the recursion relation defining $u(a, b)$,

$$u_n(a, b) \equiv c^{-1}w_n(a, b) \pmod{m}$$

for all $n \geq 0$, and m is also nondefective with respect to $u(a, b)$. □

The proof of Theorem 1.4 is a direct adaptation of the second part of the proof of Lemma 2 of [1].

Theorem 1.5. *Consider the LSFK $u(a, b)$ and the LSSK $v(a, b)$ and let p be an odd prime such that $p \nmid b$. Then $0 \in S_v(p)$ if and only if $z_u(p)$ is even.*

This follows from results in [5, pp. 42, 47]. See also Theorem 1.10 of [7].

Remark 1.6. As a consequence of Theorem 1.4, the set of nondefective integers m with respect to $v(a, b)$ is a subset of the set of nondefective integers with respect to $u(a, b)$. It further follows from Theorems 1.5 and 1.3 that the integer m is defective with respect to $v(a, b)$ if m has an odd prime divisor p for which $p \nmid b$ and $z_u(p)$ is odd.

Theorem 1.7. *Consider the LSFK $u(a, b)$ with discriminant D . Let $\gcd(a, b) = 1$ and let p be a fixed odd prime such that $p \nmid b$ and let m be a fixed positive integer such that $\gcd(m, b) = 1$. Let $z = z_u(p)$ and $\lambda = \lambda_u(p)$.*

- (i) *If $r \mid s$, then $u_r \mid u_s$.*
- (ii) *If $d = \gcd(r, s)$, then $\gcd(u_r, u_s) = |u_d|$.*
- (iii) *$z > 1$ and $z \mid p - (D/p)$, where (D/p) denotes the Legendre symbol.*

- (iv) If $p \mid D$, then $z = p$.
- (v) $u_n \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$ if and only if $z_u(m) \mid n$.
- (vi) If $z_u(p^2) \neq z_u(p)$, then $z_u(p^e) = p^{e-1}z_u(p)$ for $e \geq 2$.
- (vii) If $n \geq 1$ is such that $\gcd(m, n) = 1$, then $z_u(mn) = \text{lcm}(z_u(m), z_u(n))$.
- (viii) If $(D/p) = 1$, then $\lambda \mid p - 1$.

Proof. We note that $z > 1$, since $u_0 = 0$ and $u_1 = 1$. Part (i) follows from the Binet formulas in (3) and (4). Part (ii) is proved in Theorem VI of [5]. Parts (iii) and (viii) are proved in [5, pp. 44–45] and [9, pp. 290, 296, 297]. Part (iv) is proved in [7, p. 424]. Part (v) follows from part (ii). Part (vi) is proved in [5, p. 42]. Part (vii) follows from part (i) and (v). \square

Consider the LSFK $u(a, b)$ and let p be a fixed prime. By our earlier assumption, $p \nmid b$ and thus $u(a, b)$ is purely periodic modulo p . Since $u_0 = 0$, $u_1 = 1$, we see that $\lambda_u(p)$ is the least positive integer r such that $u_r \equiv 0$, $u_{r+1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$. Hence, $z_u(p) \mid \lambda_u(p)$ by Theorem 1.7 (v). Let $z = z_u(p)$. Since $u_z \equiv 0 \equiv u_{z+1} \cdot u_0$, $u_{z+1} \equiv u_{z+1} \cdot u_1 \pmod{p}$, it follows by induction and the second-order recursion relation defining $u(a, b)$ that

$$u_{z+n} \equiv u_{z+1} \cdot u_n \pmod{p} \tag{5}$$

for all $n \geq 0$. Thus by (5),

$$u_{zi+1} \equiv (u_{z+1})^i u_1 \equiv (u_{z+1})^i \pmod{p}. \tag{6}$$

We note that $\gcd(u_{z+1}, p) = 1$. If $\gcd(u_{z+1}, p) = d$, then $d \mid u_n$ for all $n \geq 0$, since it is assumed that $\gcd(b, p) = 1$. However, $u_1 = 1$, which implies that $d = 1$. Let

$$E_u(p) = \frac{\lambda_u(p)}{z_u(p)}.$$

It follows from the discussion in [6, pp. 354–355] that

$$E_u(p) = \text{ord}_p u_{z+1}, \tag{7}$$

where $\text{ord}_p m$ denoted the multiplicative order of m modulo p .

We have the following proposition.

Proposition 1.8. *Consider the LSFK $u(a, b)$ and let p be a prime such that $p \nmid b$. If $E_u(p) = p - 1$, then p is nondefective with respect to $u(a, b)$.*

Proof. Let $z = z_u(p)$. Since $E_u(p) = p - 1$, it follows from (7) that u_{z+1} is a primitive root modulo p . Noting that $u_0 = 0$, we see by (6) that

$$\{u_0\} \cup \{u_{zi+1}\}_{i=0}^{p-2}$$

is a complete system of residues modulo p . Thus, p is nondefective with respect to $u(a, b)$. \square

Lemma 1.9. *Consider the LSFK $u(a, b)$, where $\gcd(a, b) = 1$. Assume that $m_1 \mid m_2$, where $m_2 > m_1$ and $z_u(m_1) = z_u(m_2)$. Then $m_1 \notin S_u(m_2)$ and m_2 is defective. In particular, if a is even and $z_u(m_1)$ is even, then $z_u(m_1) = z_u(2m_1)$ and $2m_1$ is defective.*

This is proved in Corollary 1.6 of [16].

The recurrence $w(a, b)$ is said to be *uniformly distributed* (u.d.) modulo m if $A_w(d_1, m) = A_w(d_2, m)$ for all pairs (d_1, d_2) of residues modulo m such that $0 \leq d_1 < d_2 \leq m - 1$. It is clear that m is nondefective with respect to w if w is u.d. modulo m . Then m is said to be *purely nondefective* with respect to w if w is u.d. modulo m , while the nondefective integer m is said to be *impurely nondefective* with respect to w otherwise. In particular, 1 is always considered to be purely nondefective with respect to w . Theorem 1.10 due to Bumby [3] and Webb and Long [17] completely determines all purely nondefective integers m with respect to the recurrence $w(a, b)$ with discriminant D . In particular, it is shown that if m is purely nondefective with respect to $w(a, b)$, then $p \mid D$ for each prime divisor p of m .

Theorem 1.10. *Consider the recurrence $w(a, b)$ with discriminant D . Then*

- (i) $w(a, b)$ is uniformly distributed modulo m if and only if it is u.d. modulo all prime power factors of m . Moreover, $w(a, b)$ is u.d. modulo m if and only if $w(a, b)$ is u.d. modulo m_1 for each divisor m_1 of m .
- (ii) Suppose that p is odd. Then $w(a, b)$ is u.d. modulo p if and only if $p \mid D$ and $p \nmid a(2w_1 - aw_0)$.
- (iii) Suppose that $p = 2$. Then $w(a, b)$ is u.d. modulo 2 if and only if $2 \mid a$ and $2 \nmid w_0 + w_1$.
- (iv) If $p \geq 5$, then $w(a, b)$ is u.d. modulo p^e for $e \geq 2$ if and only if $w(a, b)$ is u.d. modulo p .
- (v) If $p = 2$, then $w(a, b)$ is u.d. modulo 2^e for $e \geq 2$ if and only if $a \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$ and $b \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.
- (vi) If $p = 3$, then $w(a, b)$ is u.d. modulo 3^e for $e \geq 2$ if and only if $a \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{3}$ and $b \equiv -1 \pmod{3}$, but $a^2 \not\equiv -b \pmod{9}$.

(vii) If $b = 1$ and $w(a, b)$ is u.d. modulo p , then $p = 2$ or $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.

Proof. Parts (i)–(vi) follow from the results in [3] and [17]. We now prove part (vii). Suppose that $w(a, 1)$ is u.d. modulo p . By parts (ii) and (iii), $D = a^2 + 4 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$, which implies that either $p = 2$ or $\left(\frac{-4}{p}\right) = \left(\frac{-1}{p}\right) = 1$ if p is odd. By Euler’s criterion, $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ if p is odd. \square

Corollary 1.11. *Consider the LSFK $u(a, b)$ and the LSSK $v(a, b)$ with discriminant D .*

- (i) $u(a, b)$ is u.d. modulo p if and only if $p \mid D$.
- (ii) If $m > 1$, then m is not purely nondefective with respect to $v(a, b)$.

Proof. Part (i) follows from Theorem 1.10 (ii) and (iii). Part (ii) follows from Theorem 1.10 (i)–(iii). \square

Corollary 1.12. *Suppose that the LSFK $u(a, b)$ is uniformly distributed modulo m . Then $z_u(m) = m$.*

Proof. Suppose that $p^i \parallel m$, where $i \geq 1$. Then by Theorem 1.10(i), $u(a, b)$ is u.d. modulo p^j for $j \in \{1, \dots, i\}$. We now see by Theorem 1.10 (ii) and (iii) that $p \mid D$. Then by Theorem 1.7 (iv), $z(p) = p$. If $i > 1$, then $z_u(p^2) \neq z_u(p)$ by Lemma 1.9. It now follows from parts (iv) and (vi) of Theorem 1.7 that $z_u(p^i) = p^i$. By Theorem 1.7 (vii), we now find that $z_u(m) = m$. \square

In the paper [16], we searched for all positive integers that are nondefective with respect to the LSFK $u(a, \pm 1)$, while in this paper, we look for all integers that are nondefective with respect to the LSSK $v(a, \pm 1)$. We now discuss why we chose to investigate the LSFK $u(a, b)$ and the LSSK $v(a, b)$ in these papers, rather than the more general recurrences $w(a, b)$, and why we limited our cases to the ones in which $b = \pm 1$. First of all, if m is nondefective with respect to the recurrence $w(a, b)$, then $0 \in S_w(p)$ for each prime divisor p of m by Theorem 1.3. For the LSFK $u(a, b)$ and the LSSK $v(a, b)$, it is easy to determine when $0 \in S_u(p)$ or $0 \in S_v(p)$. For the LSFK $u(a, b)$, this is trivial, since $u_0 = 0$. Clearly, $0 \in S_v(2)$, since $v_0 = 2$. Theorem 1.5 gives an easy and efficient criterion to determine when $0 \in S_v(p)$. However, for the general recurrence $w(a, b)$, there is no known efficient criterion to ascertain when $0 \in S_w(p)$ in all cases.

We now address the issue concerning why we only consider the cases in which $b = \pm 1$. By Theorem 1.4, if m is nondefective with respect to $w(a, b)$, then m is nondefective with respect to $u(a, b)$. Thus, one need only consider the LSFK $u(a, b)$ when looking for all possible nondefective integers with respect to the recurrence $w(a, b)$. By Theorem 1.3, if m is nondefective with respect to $u(a, b)$, then each prime divisor p of m is nondefective with respect to $u(a, b)$. When $b = \pm 1$, we saw

by Theorems 1.1 and 1.2 that the search for all nondefective integers with respect to $u(a, b)$ was rendered tractable, since only finitely many primes p could be nondefective with respect to $u(a, b)$ when $D \neq 0$, and in particular, these nondefective primes p are small when $p \nmid D$. In particular, by Theorem 1.1., if p is nondefective with respect to $u(a, 1)$, then $p \leq 7$ or $p \mid D = a^2 + 4$, while by Theorem 1.2, if p is nondefective with respect to $u(a, -1)$, then $p \leq 3$ or $p \mid D = a^2 - 4$.

The situation appears to be quite different when b is a fixed integer such that $b \notin \{-1, 0, 1\}$. In this case, it is highly plausible that there exist infinitely many primes p for which p is nondefective with respect to $u(a, b)$ for some integer a . This would tend to make the problem of determining all nondefective integers with respect to $u(a, b)$ unmanageable. We need only consider the case in which $(D/p) = -1$. When $(D/p) = 1$, then $\lambda_u(p) \mid p - 1$ by Theorem 1.7 (viii), and p must be defective in this case. If $(D/p) = 0$ and $D \neq 0$, then there are only finitely many primes p such that $p \mid D$. We exclude the case in which $D = 0$, because we are considering LSSK's $v(a, b)$ in this paper. If $D = a^2 + 4b = 0$, then a is even, $\alpha = \beta = a/2$, and it follows from (4), that $v_n(a, b) = 2(a/2)^n$. Then p is defective with respect to $v(a, b)$ for all primes p . This follows since $1 \notin S_v(p)$ if $p \mid a$, while $0 \notin S_v(p)$ if $p \nmid a$.

We now suppose that $(D/p) = -1$. We have the following theorem, which follows from Theorem 7 of [15].

Theorem 1.13. *Let p be a fixed odd prime and let b be a fixed integer such that $p \nmid b$. Let $g = \text{ord}_p(-b)$. Let*

$$e = \gcd((p - 1)/g, p + 1).$$

Then there exists a LSFK $u(a, b)$ for which $(D/p) = -1$ and

$$E_u(p) = eg.$$

In particular, $eg = p - 1$ when $g = (p - 1)/2$ or $g = p - 1$.

We note by Proposition 1.8 that if $E_u(p) = p - 1$, then p is nondefective with respect to $u(a, b)$. We recall that p is a Sophie Germain prime if $q = 2p + 1$ is also a prime. It is conjectured that there exist infinitely many Sophie Germain primes (see [10, p. 330]). Let $b \notin \{-1, 0, 1\}$ be a fixed integer and let p be a Sophie Germain prime such that $q = 2p + 1 \geq |b| + 2$. Since the only positive divisors of $q - 1$ are 1, 2, p , and $2p$, and since $b \notin \{-1, 0, 1\}$, we see that $\text{ord}_q(-b) = (q - 1)/2$ when $(-b/q) = 1$ and $\text{ord}_q(-b) = q - 1$ when $(-b/q) = -1$. It then follows from Theorem 1.13 that q is nondefective with respect to $u(a, b)$ for some integer a . Hence, if there exist infinitely many Sophie Germain primes p , then there would exist infinitely many primes $q = 2p + 1$ for which there exist an integer a such that q is nondefective with respect to $u(a, b)$.

2. The Main Theorems

Theorem 2.1 due to Burr [4] completely determines all nondefective integers m with respect to the Fibonacci sequence.

Theorem 2.1. *Consider the Fibonacci sequence $\{F_n\}$. Then m is nondefective if and only if m has one of the following forms:*

$$5^k, 2 \cdot 5^k, 4 \cdot 5^k, 3^j \cdot 5^k, 6 \cdot 5^k, 7 \cdot 5^k, 14 \cdot 5^k, \tag{8}$$

where $k \geq 0$ and $j \geq 1$. Moreover, m is purely nondefective if and only if m is of the form 5^k .

Theorem 2.2 due to Avila and Chen [1] complements Theorem 2.1 by finding all nondefective integers m for the Lucas sequence $\{L_n\} = v(1, 1)$.

Theorem 2.2. *Consider the Lucas sequence $\{L_n\}$. Then m is nondefective if and only if m is equal to one of the following numbers:*

$$1, 2, 4, 6, 7, 14, 3^k,$$

where $k \geq 1$.

Theorems 2.3 and 2.4 below generalize Burr’s result for the LSFK’s $u(a, 1)$ and $u(a, -1)$ and can be extracted from results appearing in [16].

Theorem 2.3. *Consider the LSFK $u(a, 1)$ with discriminant $D = a^2 + 4$. Let L be the set of integers $\ell \geq 1$ such that each prime divisor of ℓ also divides $a^2 + 4$ and $4 \nmid \ell$. If m is nondefective with respect to $u(a, 1)$, then m is in L or m is of the form*

$$2\ell, 3^k\ell, 4\ell, 6\ell, 7\ell, 14\ell, \tag{9}$$

or possibly, if $5 \nmid D$, of the form $5^k\ell$, with ℓ odd in L , and $k \geq 0$. Moreover the following holds:

- (i) ℓ is nondefective for each integer $\ell \in L$. Moreover, a is even if $2 \mid \ell$.
- (ii) 2ℓ (ℓ odd) is nondefective if and only if a is odd.
- (iii) 3ℓ is nondefective if and only if ℓ is odd and $a \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{3}$.
- (iv) $3^k\ell$ is nondefective for $k \geq 2$ if and only if ℓ is odd, and $a \equiv \pm 1$ or $\pm 2 \pmod{9}$.
- (v) 4ℓ is nondefective if and only if ℓ is odd and $a \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{4}$.
- (vi) If $5 \nmid a^2 + 4$, then 5ℓ is nondefective if and only if ℓ is odd and $a \equiv \pm 2 \pmod{5}$.

- (vii) If $5 \nmid a^2 + 4$, then $5^k \ell$ is nondefective for $k \geq 2$ if and only if ℓ is odd, $a \equiv \pm 2 \pmod{5}$, but $a \not\equiv \pm 7 \pmod{25}$.
- (viii) 6ℓ is nondefective if and only if ℓ is odd and $a \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{6}$.
- (ix) 7ℓ is nondefective if and only if ℓ is odd, and $a \equiv \pm 1$ or $\pm 3 \pmod{7}$.
- (x) 14ℓ is nondefective if and only if ℓ is odd, and $a \equiv \pm 1$ or $\pm 3 \pmod{14}$.

Theorem 2.4. Consider the LSFK $u(a, -1)$ with discriminant $D = a^2 - 4$. Let L' be the set of odd integers $\ell' \geq 1$ such that each prime divisor of ℓ' divides $a^2 - 4$ and is greater than or equal to 5. If m is nondefective, then m is of the form

$$2^i 3^j \ell', \tag{10}$$

where $i \geq 0$, $j \geq 0$, and $\ell' \in L'$. Moreover, m is nondefective if and only if one of the following cases holds:

- (i) $m = \ell'$, $2\ell'$, or $3\ell'$,
- (ii) $m = 6\ell'$ and $a \equiv 2, 3$, or $4 \pmod{6}$.
- (iii) $m = 2^i \ell'$, $i \geq 2$, and $a \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$.
- (iv) $m = 3^j \ell'$, $j \geq 2$, and $a \equiv \pm 2$ or $\pm 4 \pmod{9}$,
- (v) $m = 3 \cdot 2^i$, $i \geq 2$, and $a \equiv \pm 2 \pmod{12}$,
- (vi) $m = 2 \cdot 3^j$, $j \geq 2$, and $a \equiv \pm 2$ or $\pm 4 \pmod{18}$.
- (vii) $m = 2^i 3^j$, $i \geq 2$, $j \geq 2$, and $a \equiv \pm 2$ or $\pm 14 \pmod{36}$.

The principal results in this paper, given in Theorems 2.5 and 2.7, extend Theorem 2.2 to all LSSK's $u(a, \pm 1)$ in an analogous manner to the way in which Theorems 2.3 and 2.4 generalized Theorem 2.1 to all LSFK's $u(a, \pm 1)$.

Theorem 2.5. Consider the LSSK $v(a, 1)$. If m is nondefective, then m is one of the following numbers:

$$1, 2, 4, 6, 7, 14, 3^k, \tag{11}$$

where $k \geq 1$. Moreover, the following holds:

- (i) 2 is nondefective if and only if 4 is nondefective if and only if a is odd.
- (ii) 3 is nondefective if and only if $a \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{3}$.
- (iii) 3^k is nondefective for $k \geq 2$ if and only if $a \equiv \pm 1$ or $\pm 2 \pmod{9}$.
- (iv) 6 is nondefective if and only if $a \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{6}$.

(v) 7 is nondefective if and only if $a \equiv \pm 1$ or $\pm 3 \pmod{7}$.

(vi) 14 is nondefective if and only if $a \equiv \pm 1$ or $\pm 3 \pmod{14}$.

Moreover no $m > 1$ is purely nondefective.

Theorem 2.5 will be proved in Section 4.

Corollary 2.6. *Consider the LSSK $v(a, 1)$. Then there exists a nondefective integer m satisfying each of the possible cases in Theorem 2.5 if and only if*

$$a \equiv 1, 11, 17, 25, 29, 43, 53, 55, 71, 73, 83, 97, 101, 109, 115 \text{ or } 125 \pmod{126}.$$

Proof. This follows from Theorem 2.5 and the Chinese Remainder Theorem. \square

Theorem 2.7. *Consider the LSSK $v(a, -1)$. If m is nondefective, then m is one of the following numbers*

$$1, 2, 3, 6. \tag{12}$$

Moreover, the following holds:

(i) 2 is nondefective if and only if a is odd.

(ii) 3 is nondefective if and only if $a \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$.

(iii) 6 is nondefective if and only if $a \equiv 3 \pmod{6}$.

Moreover, no $m > 1$ is purely nondefective.

Theorem 2.7 will be proved in Section 4.

Corollary 2.8. *Consider the LSSK $v(a, -1)$. Then there exists a nondefective integer m satisfying each of the possible cases in Theorem 2.7 if and only if*

$$a \equiv 3 \pmod{6}.$$

Proof. This follows from Theorem 2.7 and the Chinese Remainder Theorem. \square

3. Auxiliary Lemmas

The following results will be needed for the proofs of our main theorems, Theorem 2.5 and Theorem 2.7.

Lemma 3.1. *Consider the LSK $u(a, b)$ and the LSSK $v(a, b)$. Then $\gcd(u_n, v_n) \mid 2$ for all $n \geq 0$.*

This is proved in Theorem II of [5].

Lemma 3.2. *Consider the LSFK $u(a, b)$ and LSSK $v(a, b)$, where a and b are both odd. Then u_n and v_n are both even or both odd according as n is or is not a multiple of 3.*

This is proved in Theorem III of [5].

Lemma 3.3. *Consider the LSSK $v(a, b)$ with discriminant $D = a^2 + 4b$. If $\gcd(m, D) > 1$, then m is defective.*

Proof. Let $u = u(a, b)$. Suppose that $\gcd(m, D) > 1$ and let $p \mid \gcd(m, D)$. If p is odd, then $z_u(p) = p$ by Theorem 1.7 (iv). Hence, $0 \notin S_v(p)$ by Theorem 1.5, and m is defective by Theorem 1.3.

Now suppose that $p = 2$. Then $2 \mid D$, which implies that a is even. Then v_n is even for all $n \geq 0$ and 2 is defective. This again implies that m is defective by Theorem 1.3. \square

Lemma 3.4. *Consider the LSFK $u(a, b)$ and the LSSK $v(a, b)$. Suppose that m is nondefective with respect to $u(a, b)$.*

- (i) *If m is odd, then m is nondefective with respect to $v(a, b)$ if and only if $0 \in S_v(m)$.*
- (ii) *If m is even, then m is nondefective with respect to $v(a, b)$ if and only if both a is odd and $0 \in S_v(m)$.*

Proof. We note that if m is nondefective with respect to $v(a, b)$, then $0 \in S_v(m)$.

Suppose that $v_r \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$ for some nonnegative integer r . Let $c = v_{r+1}$. We will show that $\gcd(c, m) = 1$ when either condition (i) or (ii) is satisfied. If $\gcd(c, m) = 1$, then it follows by the recursion relation (1) defining both $u(a, b)$ and $v(a, b)$ and the fact that $u_0 = 0, u_1 = 1$, that

$$v_{n+r} \equiv cu_n \pmod{m}$$

for all $n \geq 0$. Since $\gcd(c, m) = 1$, we see that m is nondefective with respect to $v(a, b)$ when m is nondefective with respect to $u(a, b)$.

We now demonstrate that indeed $\gcd(c, m) = 1$. First suppose that m is odd, $v_r \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$, and $\gcd(v_{r+1}, m) = d > 1$. Noting that $\gcd(b, m) = 1$, we observe by induction and the recursion relation defining $v(a, b)$ that $d \mid v_n$ for all $n \geq 0$. In particular, $d \mid v_0 = 2$. This is impossible, since m is odd and $d \mid m$.

Now suppose that m is even, a is odd and $v_r \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$. Let $d = \gcd(v_{r+1}, m)$. Arguing as above, we find that $d \mid v_n$ for all $n \geq 0$. In particular, $d \mid \gcd(v_0, v_1) = \gcd(2, a) = 1$. Hence $d = 1$ and the result follows.

Finally suppose that m and a are even. Then $D = a^2 + 4b$ is even. It now follows from Lemma 3.3 that m is defective. \square

The idea of the proof above is a direct adaptation of Lemma 2 of [1].

Lemma 3.5. *Consider the LSFK $u(a, b)$ and the LSSK $v(a, b)$ and let p be a fixed odd prime.*

(i) *Let $r = z_u(p^i)$, where $i \geq 1$, and suppose that r is even. Then $p^i \mid v_{r/2}$.*

(ii) *Suppose that a is odd and let $s = z_u(2p^i)$, where $i \geq 1$. Suppose that s is even. Then $2p^i \mid v_{s/2}$.*

Proof. (i) It follows from the Binet formulas (3) that $u_r = u_{r/2}v_{r/2}$. Then $u_{r/2} \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p^i}$ by the definition of $z_u(p^i)$. By Lemma 3.1, $\gcd(u_{r/2}, v_{r/2}) \mid 2$. Thus, $v_{r/2} \equiv 0 \pmod{p^i}$.

(ii) Similarly to the proof of part (i), we have that $u_s = u_{s/2}v_{s/2}$ and $u_{s/2} \not\equiv 0 \pmod{2p^i}$. Since $2 \mid u_s$, we see by Lemma 3.2 that $3 \mid s$. Thus $3 \mid \frac{s}{2}$. Hence, by Lemma 3.2, $2 \mid u_{s/2}$ and $2 \mid v_{s/2}$. Since $\gcd(u_{s/2}, v_{s/2}) \mid 2$, it follows that $2p^i \mid v_{s/2}$. □

Lemma 3.6. *Consider the LSSK $v(a, 1)$, where a is odd. Then $v_3 \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$.*

Proof. By inspection, we see that $v_3 = a(a^2 + 3) \equiv a(1 + 3) \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$. □

4. Proofs of the Main Theorems

We prove Theorems 2.5 and 2.7 together.

Proof of Theorems 2.5 and 2.7. Let $b = \pm 1$. It follows from Corollary 1.11 (ii) that if $m > 1$, then m is not purely nondefective with respect to $v(a, \pm 1)$. We note that the rank of 5 in $u(a, 1)$ is 3 when $a \equiv \pm 2 \pmod{5}$. It now follows from Theorems 2.3 and 2.4, Remark 1.6, Theorem 1.7 (iv), and Lemma 3.3, that if m is nondefective with respect to $v(a, b)$, then m is one of the numbers given in (11) or (12) according as $b = 1$ or $b = -1$.

Part (i) of Theorem 2.5 and part (i) of Theorem 2.7 follow from Lemmas 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, and 3.6 and the fact that $2 \mid D = a^2 + 4b$ if a is even. We note by inspection that for the LSFK $u(a, 1)$, the rank of 3 is 4 when $a \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{3}$, the rank of 6 is 12 when $a \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{6}$, the rank of 7 is 8 when $a \equiv \pm 1$ of $\pm 3 \pmod{7}$, and the rank of 14 is 24 when $a \equiv \pm 1$ or $\pm 3 \pmod{14}$. It now follows from Theorem 1.7 (vi) and inspection that for the LSFK $u(a, 1)$, the rank of 3^k is $4 \cdot 3^{k-1}$ when $k \geq 2$. Moreover, we find that for the LSFK $u(a, -1)$, the rank of 3 is 2 when $a \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ and the rank of 6 is 6 when $a \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{6}$.

The remainder of Theorem 2.5 and Theorem 2.7 now follows from Lemma 3.4 and Lemma 3.5. □

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